

Original Article

BUSINESS EDUCATORS' PERCEPTIONS ON THE UTILIZATION OF E-LEARNING TECHNOLOGIES FOR EFFECTIVE TEACHING IN UNIVERSITIES IN SOUTH EAST OF NIGERIA*Ugwu, Ikenna Vitalis and Nwokike F.O.*

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Abstract

The main purpose of the study was to determine the Business Educators' perception in the utilization of e-learning technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East States of Nigeria. The study was guided by two research question and two null hypotheses. The population was 95 Business Educators selected from 8 public tertiary institutions offering Business Education in South East States of Nigeria. Census sampling was used since the population was of manageable size. The instrument used for data collection was a 22-item questionnaire developed by the researcher. The instrument was validated by three experts and the reliability of the instrument was determined using Crombach Alpha which yielded reliability index of 0.77. The instrument was administered by the researcher and three research assistants. 82 out of 95 copies of questionnaire were well responded to, returned and used for data analysis representing 88.17 percent return rate. Mean and standard deviation were used for data analysis and t-test statistics was used to test the null hypotheses. Findings show that Business Educators' have positive perception on the utilization of e-learning hardware instant messaging technologies for effective teaching of business education in digital era in universities. The null hypotheses showed that there is no significant difference regarding the items on the mean scores of male and female Business Educators' perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware and instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria. Based on the finding it was recommended among others that Business Educators should develop their individual capacity on the e-learning technologies for effective instructional delivery and that the government and concerned bodies in education should provide e-learning technologies and complementing facilities for effective instructional delivery in universities.

Keywords: Business Educators, Perceptions, e-learning Technologies, Effective Teaching.

Introduction

The major process of achieving sustainable development of any nation for global competitiveness is through education. Education is the practice of advancing learning or the inculcation of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs and manners to individuals. Education according to Onyebuenyi, Mbah and Odeluga (2017) provides a means of transferring ideas, cultural values, norms and

livelihood to the members of the society. Education may exist in various forms among which are informal and formal educations. While Informal education according to Council of Europe (2023), covers a lifelong learning process, whereby each individual acquires attitudes, values, skills and knowledge from the educational influences and resources in his or her own environment and from daily experience. The formal education encompasses

teaching, training, narration, deliberation and guided research in a formal and organized manner. Formal education is usually taken under the guidance of educators or academics; however learners can also educate themselves nowadays, anywhere without any limitations of territorial borders. Formal education is commonly divided into numerous progressive phases such as pre-school or kindergarten, primary school, secondary school, and tertiary education. The tertiary education system covers the universities, colleges of Education, monotronics and polytechnics.

University may be defined as tertiary institution that awards degree to students in different disciplines at sub-professional, professional and training of high level manpower (Ugwu 2024). Accordingly, Ugwu, Eya and Aruah (2024) opined that university is an institution that combines teaching, research and service to society, producing graduates equipped with skills, knowledge and value for the global market. The National Universities Commission (NUC) is the regulatory body for universities in Nigeria. Universities may exist as federal, state and private owned and managed universities. While those universities owned and managed by federal and state governments are referred to as public universities, those owned and managed by private individuals are known as private universities. These universities are expected to provide training to the students in contemporary issues, curriculum contents as well as entrepreneurship irrespective of economic and environmental challenges at different programmes (Ezeabii and Agomuo, 2017). Among the programmes offered to students in universities includes Business Education.

Business Education as a programme of study is design to train competent and productive workforce that would be employed or become self-employed. Idialu (2013) stated that, Business Education is a form of vocational Education that is directed towards developing the learner to become productive for paid

employment and self-employment. Business Education programme provides the students with the skills and knowledge about business and for business activities. According to Ezeabii (2017), Business Education is an aspect of vocational Education which equips individuals with the necessary skills and theoretical knowledge needed for performance in the business world either for job performance or for self-employment. Business Education courses are taught by the Business Educators in universities and colleges of education aimed at equipping the learners with teaching, entrepreneurship, business and other office related skills. Moreover, Ndelekute and Onoh (2018) pointed that the teaching of Business Education courses is not gender sensitive as both genders can teach and equally learn the course. Business Education students at the end of their training are expected to be competent and dynamic business teachers, office administrators, business men and women that will effectively function in business world.

Business Education programme is designed to prepare the students adequately for the purpose of office work or self-employment after graduation. Teaching is the practice implemented by a teacher aimed at transmitting skills to a learner, a student, or any other audience in the context of an educational institution (Wiki 2023). Learning is the consequences of teaching, and for learning to take place, there must be an effective teaching. According to Indeed (2023), effective teaching is a term used to describe the knowledge, strategies and conduct of a successful educator. The author continued that effective teaching is the ability to make a positive impact on a student's life and academic career, including the capacity to teach important skill sets, introduce new concepts and manage any classroom concerns. Accordingly, Ugwu (2024) opined that effective teaching brings about positive change in the learner. To achieve effective teaching in our contemporary educational system, the use of physical method of curriculum delivery is no longer

adequately enough hence, the necessity for electronic means of curriculum delivery otherwise known as e-learning. This is so because e-learning enables bulk curriculum delivery and engages wide range of audience, students or learners at same time irrespective of location.

In an attempt to give opportunities to learners irrespective of their schedule and or location, e-learning was introduced. E-learning is the use of different electronic platform to acquire, deliver instruction or participate in every teaching and learning programme. E-learning according to Chikurteva, Spasova and Chikurtev (2020) is defined as technology-based learning in which learning materials are delivered electronically to distance learners via a computer network. Mbah and Ezeilo (2019) pointed that e-learning embraces several domains including, computer-based training, online learning, and m-learning, where mobile technologies are employed.

E-learning of all kinds utilizes different hardware and software technologies.

The hardware e-learning technology may be in the form of computers, tablets, or mobile devices with the software technologies installed to execute tasks as desired by the user. While the software technologies include, instant messages, social media, blogging, web conferencing among others (Mbah and Odike, 2021). Instant messaging is electronic communication platform that permits individual to assess information from another person using their personal contact (phone number, address or link). Instant messaging covers electronic messaging systems such as text message and such other social media instant messaging platforms like whatsapp, e-mail, e-portfolios and so on (Ugwu 2024). Instant messaging programs allow users to conduct online dialogue by means of typing messages back and forth to one another within specialized portions of one's computer screen (Emmanuel, 2017).

The teaching of Business Education courses in digital era demands the use of these technologies but

mostly needed for effective teaching. Research finding by Okoye and Ifejika (2017) showed that, Business Educators utilize e-learning technologies to a low extent and this low extent affected effective teaching and learning situation. The findings of the authors showed that gender and status of institution had no influence on the low extent of utilization of e-learning technologies in Business Education programme. The question is; what is their perception on utilization of e-learning technologies? Perception is a psychological concept that determines the view of individual using the five sensory organs on an item, tool, situation or event. If the Business Educators' perception of e-learning technology is improved positively, they will appreciate and utilize them in teaching, supervising and assessing of the learning outcome especially as it is believed to achieve effective teaching and learning condition. Business Educators are men and women equipped with necessary academic qualifications, skills, knowledge and values to train, groom, guide and nurture students in the field of Business of Education. The in-depth knowledge and proper qualification in the field qualifies individuals to teach the course since the teaching of Business Education is not gender based. This is so as Ndelekute and Onoh (2018) pointed out that the teaching of Business Education courses is not gender sensitive as both genders can teach and equally learn the course. Gender according to Ugwu (2024), refers to the fact of being a male or a female.

The Business Educators are expected to deliver their instructions in open distance learning in the various universities in South-East for effectiveness in the training of the students. South-East is one of the geopolitical zones in Nigeria with five states. It is known as Igbo speaking area of Nigeria with high economic and entrepreneurial development that demand the services of Business Education graduates. The training of these graduates may have been affected by the low extent of utilization of e-learning technologies. It is on the background that

the need arose to determine the perception of Business Educators in the utilization of e-learning technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East States of Nigeria.

Statement of the Problem

The e-learning activities were carried out by universities and other higher education institutions with many challenges from institutional management, ICT staff, lecturers, and students alike. E-learning gained popularity mainly because of its flexibility in delivering education and accessing content and learning resources. University Education which is structured to be flexible in curriculum content delivery requires the use of e-learning for effectiveness.

In Business Education programme in universities, there is no empirical evidence that e-learning technologies have been utilized to a high extent in improving teaching and learning for effectiveness. The implementation and utilization of e-learning technologies in Business Education could afford the lecturers the opportunities to effectively deliver instructional content to students irrespective of distance. This application could be extended in open distant learning where the lecturers interact with learners using e-learning platforms. The challenge of implementing teaching and learning of Business Education contents with the use e-learning facilities has become a worry as Business Educators are required to teach their students irrespective of time and location. Business Educators and other lecturers were unable to successfully carryout instruction and assessment of their students using the various electronic platforms available which is panacea for effective teaching in our universities to be attained. The researcher is worried about the findings of Okoye and Ifejika (2017) that Business Educators utilize e-learning technologies to a low extent in teaching. This needs to be addressed if the Business Educators must contribute and remain relevant in digital era as necessitated by information technology. If effective teaching situation must be achieved in

the universities, the low extent of utilization of e-learning by Business Educators in teaching must urgently be addressed. Therefore, there is need to determine Business Educators 'perception in the utilization of e-learning technology effective teaching in universities in South-East States of Nigeria.

Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of this study was to determine the Business Educators' perception in the utilization of e-learning technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East States of Nigeria. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. determine Business Educators' perception on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria and;
2. ascertain Business Educators' perception on the utilization of instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study;

1. What are the Business Educators' perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria?
2. What are the Business Educators' perceptions on the utilization of instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria?

Null Hypotheses

The following null hypotheses were tested at .05 level of significance

HO₁ There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Educators' perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria.

HO₂ A significant difference does not exist on the mean scores of male and female Business Educators' perception on the utilization of instant messaging

technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria.

Method

The design adopted for this study was a descriptive survey research design. A descriptive survey research design according to Alio (2008) and Nworgu (2015) is one in which a group of people or items are studied by collecting and analyzing data from only a few people or items considered to be representative of the entire population. This design was used because it involves the assessment of public opinion using questionnaire and sample methods. The study was conducted in all the public tertiary institutions in South East of Nigeria offering Business Education programme. The population was 95 Business Educators selected from 8 public tertiary institutions offering Business Education in South East States of Nigeria. Census sampling was used since the population was of manageable size.

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire designed by the researcher from the reviewed literature. The instrument was divided into two categories (A and B); category A contained the personal data of the respondents while B contained 22 items of questionnaire grouped into two sub-sections according to the research questions that guided the study. The instrument was based on four point rating scale of Strongly Agree (4), Agree (3), Disagree (2) and Strongly Disagree (1)

The instrument was face-validated by three experts. Two experts from Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education and the other one from measurement and Evaluation option, Department of Science and Computer Education all in the Faculty of Education, Enugu State University of Science and

Technology. A reliability test was conducted using 20 Business Educators in Delta and Edo States. Universities in Delta and Edo States were used because the States have the same ideology and educational policies as Enugu State. The reliability of the instrument was conducted using Cronbach Alpha and the reliability co-efficient yielded 0.77. Copies of the questionnaire were distributed by the researcher and three research assistants who were briefed on how to administer the questionnaire. Out of the 95 copies administered, 82 copies were properly filled and therefore used for data analysis representing 88.17% return rate.

Mean and Standard Deviation were used for answering the research questions. While t-test statistics was used to test the null hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The decision for the mean was based on the principle of real limits.

Thus; 3.50 - 4.00 Strongly Agree

2.50 - 3.49 Agree

1.50 - 2.49 Disagree

1.00 - 1.49 Strongly Disagree

In testing the hypotheses, when the value of calculated “t” is equal or greater than the given table t-value, the null hypothesis was rejected, otherwise do not reject.

Results

The results are presented in tables 1 to 4 according to the research questions and null hypothesis that guided the study.

Research Question 1

What are the Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria?

Table 1: Mean scores and standard deviation of Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria N=82

S/N	Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies includes;	Male N=22		Female N=60		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
1	Using magnetic white board in video conferencing	3.09	0.92	2.95	0.95	2.99	0.94	Agree
2	Preparing instruction with laptop	3.36	0.58	3.25	0.60	3.28	0.59	Agree
3	Delivering business education instruction with projectors	2.91	1.06	2.82	0.98	2.84	0.99	Agree
4	Using smart phone in communicating to students	3.36	0.58	3.35	0.63	3.35	0.62	Agree
5	Operating palmtop/tablets in e-learning condition	3.55	0.51	3.58	0.49	3.57	0.50	Strongly Agree
6	Making use of video machines/webcam in video conferencing	3.27	0.46	3.28	0.64	3.28	0.59	Agree
7	Using torch pads in e-learning conditions	3.14	0.64	3.13	0.65	3.13	0.64	Agree
8	Applying the use of apple clouds for lecturing	3.05	0.49	3.08	0.65	3.07	0.60	Agree
9	Making use of desktop computer and VDU to deliver lectures	3.05	0.72	2.97	0.90	2.99	0.85	Agree
10	Using removable disk (flash drive, compact disk, external hard disk etc)	3.09	0.53	3.27	0.58	3.22	0.57	Agree
Cluster Mean/SD		3.19	0.65	3.17	0.71	3.46	0.69	Agree

X= Mean; SD = Standard Deviation; HN = Highly Needed
 The analysis of data presented in Table 1 above shows item 5 has mean rating of 3.57 and standard deviation of 0.50 depicting strongly agree. The remaining nine items overall mean ratings range from 2.84 to 3.35 showing agree. This means that the Business Educators’ in their perceptions agree on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria. The overall cluster mean of 3.46 further indicates that the items are the Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of

e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria. The low standard deviation of 0.69 indicates that the respondents have similar opinion to the items.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant difference between the mean scores of male and female Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria.

Table 2: Summary of t-test analysis of mean scores of male and female Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria

Variables	N	t	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	22	0.198	80	.843	.18030	.90878	NS
Female	60						

The result of t-test analysis in Table 2 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significant and 80 degree of freedom for the items is 0.198 with a significant value of 0.843. Since the significant value of 0.843 is more than the 0.05 level of significant the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference regarding the items on the mean ratings of male and female Business

Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria.

Research Question 2

What are the Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria?

Table 3: Mean scores and standard deviation on the Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria N=82

S/N	Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of instant messaging technologies includes;	Male N=22		Female N=60		Overall		Decision
		\bar{X}_1	SD ₁	\bar{X}_2	SD ₂	\bar{X}_G	SD _G	
11.	Creating a WhatsApp group for the class instruction	3.18	0.80	3.52	0.70	3.43	0.74	Agree
12.	Sharing videos, pdf/audio instruction through WhatsApp	3.05	0.65	3.08	0.59	3.07	0.60	Agree
13.	Organizing an interactive WhatsApp chatting on a topic prior to instruction	2.82	1.01	2.85	1.10	2.84	1.07	Agree
14.	Using e-mails to deliver instructions to the students	2.91	0.75	3.03	0.78	3.00	0.77	Agree
15.	Creating a blog for the audio/video instruction	2.77	0.81	2.97	0.80	2.91	0.80	Agree
16.	Uploading of instructional contents to dedicated electronic mail	2.77	0.75	2.78	0.92	2.78	0.88	Agree
17.	Establishing a forum using yahoo messenger	3.05	0.84	3.17	0.85	3.13	0.84	Agree
18.	Creating a bulk message platform for communicating to students.	2.73	0.70	2.70	0.85	2.71	0.81	Agree
19.	Using instant message as a substitute for physical learning	3.00	0.69	2.88	0.85	2.91	0.80	Agree
20.	Using instant message in monitoring student’s participation in group learning	3.09	0.68	3.07	0.86	3.07	0.81	Agree
21.	Using it as a platform for collecting assignment	3.23	0.69	3.10	0.89	3.13	0.84	Agree
22.	Utilizing instant message in conducting oral/written examination	2.91	0.61	2.93	0.76	2.93	0.72	Agree
Cluster Mean/SD		3.23	0.82	3.28	0.90	3.26	0.88	Agree

X= Mean: SD = Standard Deviation

The data presented in Table 3 indicates that the overall item mean scores ranges from 2.71 to 3.43 revealing agree. This shows that the items are the

Business Educators’ perceptions agree on the utilization of instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of

Nigeria. The overall cluster mean score of 3.26 indicates agree. The low standard deviation of 0.65 shows that the respondent’s opinions do not differ remarkably to the itemized Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria.

Table 4: Summary of t-test analysis of mean ratings of male and female Business Educators’ perception on the utilization of instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria

Variables	N	t	df	Sig. (2tailed)	Mean Difference	Std. Error Difference	Decision
Male	22	0.350	80	.727	0.58333	1.66500	NS
Female	60						

The result of t-test analysis in Table 4 shows that the t-value at 0.05 level of significant and 80 degree of freedom for the items is 0.350 with a significant value of 0.727. As the significant value of 0.727 is more than the 0.05 level of significant the null hypothesis is not significant. This means that there is no significant difference with respect to the items on the mean ratings of male and female Business Educators’ perception on the utilization of instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria.

Discussion of Findings

Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities include using magnetic white board in video conferencing, preparing instruction with laptop, delivering business education instruction with projectors, using smart phone in communicating to students, operating palmtop/tablets in e-learning condition, making use of video machines/webcam in video conferencing, using torch pads in e-learning conditions, Applying the use of apple clouds for lecturing, making use of desktop computer and VDU to deliver lectures and using removable disk (flash drive, compact disk, external hard disk etc). The findings from this study are in consonance with Singh and Tumanishvili

Hypothesis 2

A significant difference does not exist on the mean ratings of male and female Business Educators’ perception on the utilization of instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria.

(2021) stated that e-learning creates, uses, and manages technological processes and educational resources to aid and enhance academic performance of students. The findings showed that Business Educators’ have positive perception on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching of business education in digital era in universities. These perceptions will help business educators to utilize the available hardware facilities in teaching students. This implies that the identified Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities should be encourage as it would improve the quality of teaching and learning in the 21st century.

The findings of the study showed that there is no significant difference regarding the items on the mean ratings of male and female Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria. The implication of the finding was that the gender of the respondents had no significant influence on the identified Business Educators’ perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities. This was supported by Nungse and Dung (2017) and Femi (2018) which

noted that gender had no effect on the utilization of digital hardware in teaching and learning activities in the universities. Therefore, the identified items on the Business Educators' perceptions on the utilization of e-learning hardware technologies for effective teaching in universities are necessary for instructional delivery.

The study showed that Business Educators' have positive perception on the utilization of instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria. Among the Business Educators' perception on the utilization of instant messaging were; creating a WhatsApp group for the class instruction, sharing videos, pdf/audio instruction through Whatsapp, organizing an interactive WhatsApp chatting on a topic prior to instruction, using e-mails to deliver instructions to the students, creating a blog for the audio/video instruction, uploading of instructional contents to dedicated electronic mail, establishing a forum using yahoo messenger, creating a bulk message platform for communicating to students, using instant message as a substitute for physical learning, using instant message in monitoring student's participation in group learning, using it as a platform for collecting assignment and utilizing instant message in conducting oral/written examination. The findings according to the respondents showed that the instant messages are useful for effective teaching and learning of Business Education in universities. The findings of the study were supported by Chekwude (2015) that the application of instant messages in teaching helps in out of school engagement of the learners. The identified Business Educators perception on the utilization of instant messages would help to strengthen the application and positive utilization on the art of the learners. This indicated that the identified are the Business Educators perception on the utilization of instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities.

References

Furthermore, the findings of the study indicated that there was no significant difference with respect to the items on the mean ratings of male and female Business Educators' perception on the utilization of instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities in South-East of Nigeria. The implication of no significant different was that the gender had no influence on the identified Business Educators' perception on the utilization of instant messaging technologies for effective teaching in universities.

Conclusion

The study determined the Business Educators' perception in the utilization of e-learning technology effective teaching in universities. The study identified the Business Educators' perception in the utilization e-learning hardware technologies and instant massaging technologies for effective teaching in universities. The identified perception depicted that the Business Educator is utilizing these e-learning technologies for effective teaching and learning of the programme. This perception has implication to quality teaching and learning of programme in digital era as the identified utilization would enable the university authorities and government to provide the needed e-learning technologies for effective teaching and learning programme.

Recommendations

Based on the findings of the study, the following recommendations were made;

1. Business Educators should develop their individual capacity on the e-learning technologies for effective instructional delivery.
2. The government and concerned bodies in education should provide e-learning technologies and complementing facilities for effective instructional delivery in universities.

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